

Sustainable anti-UV coating to protect wooden façades

using biocarbon as UV-stabilizer

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Introduction

Sunlight is essential for life on Earth. However, part of its electromagnetic radiation spectrum can be detrimental to living organisms and materials. More specifically, ultraviolet (UV) radiation has wavelengths shorter than that of the visible region, but longer than that of X-rays, in the range of 10 nm to 400 nm, and energies from 3 eV to 124 eV. The UV spectrum can be subdivided into UVA (400–315 nm), UVB (315–280), UVC (280–100 nm) and UVD (100–10 nm) regions. While UVC and UVD are absorbed by the ozone in the Earth's atmosphere, UVA is not absorbed by ozone and represents 99% of the UV radiation that reaches the Earth's surface. UVB is mostly absorbed by ozone, with an amount of received radiation strongly dependent on the latitude and elevation of the earthly location [1]. UV radiation affects terrestrial and aquatic organisms negatively, either by directly damaging specific cellular targets or indirectly by generating reactive oxygen species [2]. With UV radiation triggering the formation of free radicals, the long-term exposure to UV radiation can result in health issues, in the case of human exposure, and discolouration, weathering, yellowing, loss of gloss and mechanical properties, in the case of various materials exposure. To preserve deterioration linked to UV exposure, UV-protective agents are needed.

In nature, living organisms display interesting UV protection mechanisms. Amongst multiple strategies, living organisms synthesize or accumulate compounds that absorb incident energy radiation in the UV range and convert it into heat, which is then dissipated without the formation of intermediate radicals. The wavelength of absorption is a property brought by a group of atoms. Two types of groups, the chromophores and auxochromes, can influence the absorption spectrum of a molecule. A chromophore group is a functional group, not conjugated with another group, which exhibits a characteristic absorption spectrum in the UV or visible region. Nitro, nitroso, azo, azo amino, azoxy, carbonyl and thiocarbonyl are some of the most important chromophoric groups. The auxochromes groups generally do not absorb significantly in the 200–800 nm region but affect the spectrum of the chromophore to which it is attached. OH, NH₂, CH₃ and NO₂ are the most important auxochromic groups. Cyanobacteria, fungi and algae synthesize mycosporine compounds having oxo-carbonyl chromophores to deal with cellular stress caused by exposure to UV radiations [3]. In plants, various UV mechanisms are combined, like damage repair that restores damaged tissue or compounds, pigment synthesis and antioxidant production. In the epidermal layer of leaves, components such as flavonoids, containing aromatic and sometimes carbonyl chromophores, and other phenolic compounds provide most of the UV protection by absorbance [4]. In high-UV dose habitats, plants commonly absorb UV radiation by the cuticular wax, and some of them use fluorophores to convert the harmful solar UV into blue light that can be utilised for photosynthesis in low-light conditions [5]. On human skin, the suntan is a defence mechanism involving the brown pigment melanin that absorbs UVA radiation to avoid damage in the tissue.

Synthetic organic and inorganic UV filters have been developed and massively commercialized for various markets. Due to their release into the aquatic environment, organic UV filters are becoming an important group of emerging contaminants, raising concerns about their impact on the environment and human health [6]. Inorganic UV absorbers based on metal oxide semiconductors (such as TiO₂, ZnO, SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ [7]) appear to be less toxic and chemically more stable than organic absorbers when exposed to both high temperature and UV. To be efficient, the bandgap of inorganic materials must be suitable for UV-radiation absorption [8]. Recently, some inorganic UV absorbers started showing safety concerns. For example, the European Union published in 2020 the official delegated regulation to

55 classify TiO₂ as a suspected carcinogen by inhalation. Hence, further research is needed to develop
56 efficient but safer and more sustainable UV absorbers.

57
58 Biocarbon (or biochar) is a carbon-based product obtained from carbonization (slow pyrolysis process)
59 of organic materials in the absence of oxygen above 300–400°C [9]. Organic materials can be wastes
60 from the agricultural or forestry industries that currently have little or no economic value. Biocarbon has
61 gained scientific interest thanks to its utilization in environmental management and its ability to mitigate
62 greenhouse gas emissions, such as sequestration of CO₂ and CH₄ in global carbon pools, and to
63 mitigate N₂O emissions, the most important ozone-depleting compound in the atmosphere [10].
64 Biocarbon from various biomass has recently shown promising light-absorbing properties for use in
65 solar-steam generation devices [11]–[15]. This application, though, focuses on wavelengths ranging
66 between 400 nm and 2500 nm and does not consider the UV radiation range. However, algae-derived
67 carbon nanodots exhibited protection properties against UV irradiation, with negligible cytotoxicity
68 towards eukaryotic cells, which made them promising for use in sunscreen formulations [16].

69
70 In this study, biocarbon particles were produced from beechwood (*Fagus sylvatica* L.). Their chemical
71 and physical characteristics were investigated, and their UV absorbance properties were assessed in
72 regard to their size. The surface of two wood species was subsequently coated with the biocarbon
73 particles dispersed in a natural drying oil, and the properties of the developed sustainable coatings were
74 studied for their use in façades or other outdoor applications.

75

76 **Materials and Methods**

77

78 **Beechwood biomass carbonization and characterization of biocarbon particles**

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80 Beechwood (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) chips were dried at 103°C for 72 hours before undergoing a
81 carbonization process via a tube furnace (Nabertherm RSRC 120-1000/13) at 500°C for 2 hours
82 (heating rate 2000°C/h) under an inert N₂ atmosphere. The yield of biocarbon was calculated from the
83 mass of biocarbon (g) and the oven-dried mass of raw material (g) [17]. To evaluate the influence of
84 particle size on UV and visible light absorption, four different size classification were produced. First,
85 one portion of the carbonized beech particles was sieved to three different size classifications (38-106
86 µm, 106-150 µm, 150-425 µm). The remaining material was transferred to stainless steel jars with 20
87 mm diameter stainless steel balls (balls to biocarbon ratio was equal to 25) and ball milled in deionized
88 water for 5 hours at 200 rpm with a planetary mill (Pulverisette 5 classic line). Short milling cycles (10
89 min on, followed by 5 min off) were repeated until achieving the required time to avoid temperature rise.
90 After milling, water was evaporated at 50°C until a constant mass was reached.

91

92 Proximate analyses were carried out on the beechwood raw biomass and carbonized particles (before
93 sieving) to determine moisture, fixed carbon, volatiles and ash content. Particle size measurements
94 were done with a particle size analyser (Horiba Scientific LA-960A2) in suspension in water after one
95 minute of ultrasound to ensure proper dispersion of the particles. The particle refractive index was taken
96 at 1.920–0.522i; these values were adapted for carbonaceous particles [18], [19]. The UV extinction of
97 water solution containing 125, 250 and 500 mg/L of biocarbon was assessed with UV-VIS
98 Spectrophotometer UV7 (Mettler Toledo). FTIR spectra were recorded using an ALPHA FT-IR
99 Spectrometer (Bruker), equipped with Wine-ATR (attenuated total reflection) module. The absorbance
100 spectra were recorded in the range of 4000–400 cm⁻¹, at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹; each spectrum
101 represents an average of 32 scans. The spectra were processed by smoothing and atmospheric noise
102 elimination using OPUS software.

103

104 **Preparation and characterization of the wood coatings**

105

106 Different tung oil-based coating formulations were prepared, containing 0, 1, 2, 5, 10 and 20 wt.%
107 (regarding the oil weight) biocarbon with the particle size occurring the most after sieving (106–150 µm)
108 as a first approach. Oak (*Quercus* sp.) and beechwood (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) samples with dimensions
109 15 x 15 x 2 cm³ were selected to have the coatings applied by hand. The weight of the wood samples
110 was measured before and after coating to estimate the thickness of the coatings. Wood coatings were
111 weathered in a QUV accelerated weathering tester (Q-lab) according to the EN 927-6 standard. The
112 colour of the coated wood samples was assessed before and after weathering with a Spektromaster
113 565-45 spectrophotometer (Erichsen, Hemer, Germany) using the CIE L*a*b* system. D65 illuminant
114 and 10° viewer angle were selected for the measurements. The reported colour values are the average

115 of three different spots. The total colour change (ΔE) induced by the weathering was calculated
 116 according to the following equation:
 117

$$118 \quad \Delta E = \sqrt{(\Delta L^*)^2 + (\Delta a^*)^2 + (\Delta b^*)^2}$$

119
 120 where ΔL , Δa , Δb correspond to differences between colour coordinate values measured at the given
 121 time and referenced to the corresponding value of initial colour.
 122

123 The wettability of the coatings was evaluated by wetting the surface with distilled water and measuring
 124 the dynamic contact angle with an optical tensiometer Attension Theta Flex Auto 4 (Biolin Scientific,
 125 Gothenburg, Sweden) equipped with a 3D Topography Module. Five measurements were performed on
 126 each specimen, with a volume of each drop set at 4 μL .
 127

128 Results and Discussion

129 Composition of raw beechwood and its biocarbon

130
 131 The yield of biocarbon obtained from the carbonization of beechwood at 500°C was 23.7%. The results
 132 of proximate analysis for the precursor beechwood biomass as well as the derived biocarbon are
 133 presented in Table 1. The amount of moisture and volatile matter sharply decreased after pyrolysis since
 134 water molecules and volatiles evaporate during the thermal process, creating a porous structure [20],
 135 [21] while ash and fixed carbon contents increased after pyrolysis. Similar volatiles and fixed carbon
 136 contents were reported by Aburas and Demirbas [22] for raw beechwood (82.5% and 17.1%,
 137 respectively). Ash consists mainly of metal oxides like SiO_2 , CaO , K_2O , P_2O_5 , Al_2O_3 and MgO [23] that
 138 originate from soil and irrigation water and were accumulated in the tree during the growth phase [24].
 139 The ash content of raw beechwood was comparable with the value found by previous research that
 140 reported 0.4% and 0.5%, respectively [22], [25]. The amount of ash in the biocarbon depends on the
 141 original feedstock [26] and the pyrolysis conditions [27], among other parameters. Ash is considered as
 142 an impurity that would decrease the efficiency of biocarbon in some applications such as adsorption of
 143 pollutants (gaseous or aqueous) [28]. Additionally, ash particles tend to settle around and inside the
 144 pores, leading to a lower surface area [29]. For these reasons, the low ash content measured for our
 145 biocarbon samples appear advantageous. Different C, O and H contents were estimated from the
 146 proximate analysis data based on the mathematical method reported in [30] (Table 1). The assessment
 147 shows that beechwood biocarbon is highly carbonaceous, with an elemental C amount of up to 80%. H-
 148 and O-containing groups were released during the pyrolysis process; therefore, the progress of the
 149 process can be described by evaluation of the molar ratios with C [23]. Functional properties of
 150 biocarbon can be reflected by the O/C and H/C ratios; the low value of the former shows that the
 151 presence of oxygen-containing functional groups and aliphatic components decreased in the biocarbon
 152 when compared with the raw biomass, and reflects a more aromatic structure [29], [31]. The obtained
 153 ratios are within the range of previously reported values according to the Van-Krevelen diagram for
 154 woody materials biocarbon prepared at 500°C [23]. As observed in plants where chromophore groups
 155 and aromatic structures provide most of the UV protection by absorbance [4], the low H/C and O/C ratios
 156 could be favorable for the UV absorbing potential of the biocarbon.
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 159

159 *Table 1 Proximate analysis of raw beechwood and its biocarbon*

	Proximate analysis				Estimated elemental composition				
Beechwood	Moisture	Volatiles	Ash	Fixed Carbon	C	O	H	O/C	H/C
	%	%	%	%	%	%	%		
Raw	8.85	76.08	0.44	14.63	50.18	35.80	5.54	1.01	2.22
Biocarbon	2.88	22.83	1.49	72.80	80.84	11.34	2.55	0.09	0.37

160 161 Particle size of the biocarbon particles 162

163 Due to the heterogeneous size of precursor biomass, the derived biocarbon usually has a broad range
 164 in terms of particle size [32]. The particle diameter at 10% (D10), 50% (D50) and 90% (D90) of the
 165 cumulative size distribution and the mean size of the biocarbon samples from the four size classifications
 166 (sieved at different sizes and ball milled) are listed in table 2.

167 *Table 2 Particles' size and representative diameters of the sieved and ball milled biocarbon fractions*

Samples	D10 (μm)	D50 (μm)	D90 (μm)	Mean Size (μm)
Sieved 150-425 μm	9.53	55.23	259.04	90.69
Sieved 106-150 μm	12.45	81.52	177.03	88.88
Sieved 38-106 μm	13.39	70.31	144.02	75.30
Ball Milled 5h	2.03	3.13	11.48	6.37

168
 169 Particles sizes are roughly distributed within the predicted interval of sieving. For the two larger sieves,
 170 the mean size and D50 were lower than the sieve size, indicating that smaller particles were trapped
 171 and not evacuated efficiently or that the ultrasound used to disperse particles also allowed to break
 172 agglomerates. The overall distribution is fitted in the micro-size range with the highest and smallest
 173 diameters being 1.5 μm and 260 μm , respectively. No nanoparticles were detected by the analysis. The
 174 mean size varied between 75.30 μm and 90.69 μm for the sieved samples and dropped at 6.37 μm for
 175 the ball milled sample. With an initial biocarbon size of 0.5 mm, ball milling effectively reduced and
 176 homogenized its particle size.

177
 178 The vibrations of functional groups in beechwood and its derivative biocarbon at different particle sizes
 179 are illustrated by FTIR spectra in Figure 1.

181
 182 *Figure 1 FTIR spectra of raw and carbonized beechwood*

183 In the raw biomass spectra, the wideband at about 3300–3450 cm^{-1} corresponded to hydroxyl (-OH)
 184 vibrations coming from water molecules and other OH groups contained in the sample [17], [27]. This
 185 band was less visible for the biocarbon samples due to the evaporation of components containing -OH
 186 groups during pyrolysis such as water, alcohol and phenols [33]. This observation was confirmed by our
 187 proximate analysis results that revealed a decrease in moisture and volatiles content for the biocarbon
 188 compared to the raw beechwood. Similar small peaks were reported for rapeseed biocarbon produced
 189 at a temperature ranging between 350°C and 550°C, for which the -OH groups at 3400 cm^{-1} were weak
 190 and tended to be negligible as the pyrolysis temperature increased above 550°C [27]. The band between
 191 2950 cm^{-1} and 2825 cm^{-1} was assigned to the presence of CH_3 asymmetric and symmetric aliphatic
 192 methylene stretching vibrations [34], [35]. This band faded in the four biocarbon's spectra. The same
 193 findings were reported by Angin et al. [34] who observed that aliphatic groups tended to disappear from
 194 safflower seed cake's biocarbon produced at 400°C and above when compared to the raw biomass.
 195 However, in another previous study, aliphatic compounds were detectable in raw sorghum bagasse
 196 feedstock as well as in its derivative biocarbon produced at temperatures ranging from 350°C to 550°C
 197 [33]. The peaks ranging between 1900 cm^{-1} and 2300 cm^{-1} confirm the presence of carboxyl and
 198 carbonyl groups [34]. The latter was very weak in the raw biomass spectrum, which is in correlation with
 199 the increase of fixed carbon content in biocarbon compared to un-carbonized beechwood according to
 200 the proximate analysis. Asymmetrical peaks in the range 1800–1750 cm^{-1} were attributed to C-O
 201 stretching in biocarbon and raw wood samples. This peak came from a variety of functional groups
 202 containing C-O, including ketones, carboxylic acids, esters and anhydrides [36], [37]. Similarly, the
 203 peaks in the range 1600–1580 cm^{-1} were attributed to the C=O stretching [17]. C=C vibrations linked to

204 the presence of alkenes and aromatics [38] also appeared in the spectra of the raw biomass between
 205 1415 cm^{-1} and 1800 cm^{-1} . Bands in the range 1050 cm^{-1} to 1350 cm^{-1} indicated the occurrence of
 206 primary, secondary and tertiary alcohols, phenols, ethers and esters containing C–O stretching and O–
 207 H deformation vibrations [36]. Bands between 1415 cm^{-1} and 1800 cm^{-1} are assigned to C=C vibration
 208 representatives of alkenes and aromatics [38]. Aromatic hydrogen structures (C–H stretching) were
 209 detected near 680 cm^{-1} and 850 cm^{-1} [34], [36] in the biocarbon spectra, while the latter was absent in
 210 the raw wood spectrum. The detection of aromatic groups in the biocarbon samples is in accordance
 211 with the decrease of O/C and H/C ratios. Indeed, low values of these molar ratios reflect the aromatic
 212 character of biocarbon specimens. The large peak around 570 cm^{-1} obtained for raw beechwood
 213 corresponds to aromatic rings [40] that might be derived from lignin polymers. This band is less visible
 214 for biocarbon samples due to the thermal degradation of lignin during the carbonization process. The
 215 FTIR analysis highlighted similar spectra for the biocarbon constituted from different particle sizes,
 216 hence the sieving or grinding process did not noticeably impact the functional groups' composition of
 217 biocarbon. Changes in FTIR profiles between raw and carbonized matter reflected the thermal
 218 treatment's effect. The difference in functional groups' composition indicated the dehydration and
 219 degradation of lignocellulosic components, the appearance of their transformation derivatives and the
 220 increase in aromatic carbon structures [27], and in chromophoric groups such as carbonyl groups.

222 Influence of the biocarbon particle size on their UV and visible light absorption properties

223
 224 Figure 2 presents the absorbance of water solutions containing dispersed biocarbon particles of the four
 225 considered particle size ranges: 150-425 μm , 106-150 μm , 38-106 μm and 0-20 μm . Three
 226 concentrations were considered for each fraction, 125, 250 and 500 mg/L for the three higher particle
 227 sizes and 50, 100 and 200 mg/L for the smaller particle size, to avoid saturation of the detector and
 228 keep absorbance values below 1. For all the solutions, the absorbance was roughly constant in the UV
 229 and visible range of the spectra. Yang et al. [11] observed a steadier absorbance in the wavelength
 230 region 400–2500 nm of carbonized algae powder when compared with its precursor biomass. The
 231 absorbance was found to be proportional to the concentration of the solution, doubling the concentration
 232 roughly doubling the absorbance for all samples. Chatzimitakos et al. [16] similarly found a direct
 233 proportion between the concentration of algal-based carbon nanodot solutions and the corresponding
 234 sun protection factor. At iso concentration, the size of the particles influenced their absorbance—the
 235 higher the particle size, the lower their absorbance. This trend was specifically verified for the smallest
 236 fraction (0-20 μm), which displayed an absorbance close to 1 at 200 mg/L, while the bigger fractions'
 237 absorbance was between 0.6 and 0.8 at 500 mg/L.
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239
 240 *Figure 2 Absorbance of dispersed biocarbon particles of various particle size ranges in water solutions*
 241 *of increasing concentrations: a) 125 mg/L, b) 250 mg/L, c) 500 mg/L*

242 Influence of the biocarbon content in the tung oil wood coating

244 Thickness and colour of the coating

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 246 The thickness of the coatings deposited by hand-coating was estimated between 259 μm (0%
 247 biocarbon) and 376 μm (20% biocarbon), with increasing biocarbon content leading to an increase in
 248 thickness. Figure 33 shows the unweathered (up) and weathered (down) uncoated (control) and coated
 249 oak and beechwood samples with an increasing biocarbon content in a tung oil base.

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Figure 3 Unweathered (up) and weathered (down) uncoated (control) and coated oak samples with increasing biocarbon content in tung oil base

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Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden. 4 shows the impact of the biocarbon content on L^* , a^* and b^* for oak and beechwood surfaces before and after weathering. In the CIE Lab system, L^* is the lightness (100 corresponds to white and 0 corresponds to black), $+a^*/-a^*$ represents the red/green tone and $+b^*/-b^*$ represents the yellow-blue tone.

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The artificial weathering cycle altered the L^* of uncoated wood samples in opposite ways. It whitened the oak and darkened the beechwood. The composition of oak/beechwood has been reported in the literature [41], and the proportion of the main wood polymer components is close in these two hardwood species (Holocellulose 78.79/75.83; Cellulose 44.72/45.35; Lignin Klason 23.71/20.49). However, the weathering induces complex phenomena with the combined effect of water, UV-light, oxygen, heat and atmospheric pollutants (mainly SO_2 , NO_2 , O_3). UV radiation initiates chemical changes on wood surfaces, leading to their discolouration and deterioration. Cellulose and lignin are sensitive to solar radiation, and lignin is the main UV-absorbing wood component, thanks to its chromophores [42]. The modification of these chromophores after absorption of UV light in the 300–400 nm range is responsible for the discolouration of wood and is associated with the formation of aromatic free-radicals that react with oxygen to produce carbonyl and carboxyl groups [43]. The degradation products of lignin contain conjugated ketones, aldehydes and quinones that lead to the darker colour of the wooden weathered surface [44]. However, the weathering cycle includes condensation steps that allow the degraded products to be washed away from the surface, leaving the cellulose apparent, more colour stable against UV light [45]. Hence, the effects of artificial weathering cannot be generalized for different wood species.

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Figure 4 Impact of the biocarbon content on L^* , a^* and b^* for unweathered (UnW) and weathered (W) uncoated (Control) and coated oak (Oak) (a, b, c) and beechwood (Beech) (d, e, f) samples

277 The application of tung oil on the wood surface, even without biocarbon, greatly decreased L^* , and
 278 increased a^* and b^* values, due to the yellow colour of the tung oil itself. This decrease is more visible
 279 in the case of beechwood whose initial colour was lighter ($L^* = 79$) than that of oak ($L^* = 63$). L^* , a^* and
 280 b^* continuously decreased with the addition of biocarbon due to its black colour. For 20% biocarbon, L^*
 281 decreased down to a value close to 18 for both types of wooden surfaces. Poohphajai et al. [46] reported
 282 CIE L^* values ranging from 23.1 to 24.0 for black coatings using biofilms. Both a^* and b^* values were
 283 close to 0 for 20% biocarbon content. After weathering, the a^* and b^* values were shifted to higher
 284 values for the coated samples at a given biocarbon content, which was attributed to the strong
 285 absorbance of tung oil for UV and visible light, especially in the range between 200 nm and 300 nm [47].
 286 The weathering cycle did not alter much the value of L^* for both wood species, thanks to the colour
 287 stabilization brought by the combined absorbance of tung oil and biocarbon particles. Total colour
 288 change (ΔE) of the coated oak and beechwood samples after weathering (Figure 5) decreased with the
 289 increase in biocarbon content, confirming the colour stability brought by the biocarbon.
 290

291 *Figure 5 Evolution of the total colour change (ΔE) of the coated oak and beechwood samples after*
 292 *weathering, as a function of the biocarbon content*
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294 **Wettability of the coating**

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 296 Surface wettability and ability to repel water can be characterized based on the water contact angle
 297 (WCA). The WCA of a water droplet deposited on the oak and beechwood control (uncoated) and coated
 298 surfaces was monitored over time (up to 60 seconds). WCA values measured after 10, 30 and 60
 299 seconds were compared. The WCA of the control samples strongly decreased over time, losing up to
 300 9% and 22% of its value between 10 and 30 seconds, and up to 14% and 32% between 10 and 60
 301 seconds, for unweathered and weathered samples, respectively. Application of the tung oil on the
 302 wooden surface led to a stabilization of the WCA over time. Indeed, the maximal WCA decrease for
 303 coated samples was measured at 4% and 5% between 10 and 60 seconds for unweathered and
 304 weathered samples, respectively. For the following assessment of the different coatings' wettability,
 305 WCAs are systematically compared after 10 seconds. Figure 6 presents the evolution of the WCA of
 306 coated oak and beechwood samples in regard to the biocarbon content.
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308 *Figure 6 WCA of coated oak and beechwood samples in regard to the biocarbon content*
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310 A surface can be categorized as super-hydrophilic when WCA = 0°, hydrophilic when WCA < 90°,
311 hydrophobic when WCA > 90° and super-hydrophobic when WCA > 150° [48]. Both uncoated
312 beechwood and oak surfaces showed a hydrophilic character with WCAs around 46° and 80°,
313 respectively. The higher WCA obtained with oak control may be due to the higher content of lignin on
314 its surface [49], making it naturally more apolar compared to beechwood. After treatment with tung oil,
315 both surfaces gained a hydrophobic property and achieved 100° and 99° for beechwood and oak,
316 respectively. Janesh et al. [50] successfully used tung oil on spruce wood boards to provide water
317 resistance. In the mentioned study, the WCA increased by up to 48%, going from 45° ± 9° to 88° ± 3°
318 for the uncoated and coated surface, respectively. Biocarbon/tung oil-coated woods displayed an
319 increase in terms of water repellence, presenting higher WCA values compared to specimens coated
320 with tung oil only. With the increase of biocarbon content, WCA continuously increased up to 138° and
321 120° for beechwood and oak, respectively, for 20% biocarbon. The achieved hydrophobicity of the
322 biocarbon/tung oil coatings can be attributed to the synergetic effect of tung oil (mentioned earlier) and
323 the increased surface's roughness brought on by the carbon particles. Indeed, according to the Wenzel
324 model's assumption [51], the coating droplets penetrate more easily into the pores developed in a rough
325 surface, which provides higher adhesive forces and increases the protective effect of the coating against
326 water, i.e. its hydrophobicity. Additionally, the hydrophobic nature of biocarbon [52], previously
327 highlighted by the moisture content measured by proximate analysis, contributes to the overall
328 hydrophobicity of the developed coatings.

329
330 WCA values were higher for coated beechwood than oak, which means that wooden surface type affects
331 the efficiency of the coating. Due to the differences in the chemical composition of wood species, their
332 adhesion with coatings can be different. Beechwood displayed better adhesive properties because of
333 its surface composition that has less hydrophobic lignin and extractives, which makes aliphatic and
334 phenolic hydroxyls more accessible for binding with coatings and has a direct effect on improving the
335 wettability [53]. However, on the oak surface, these hydroxyl groups are occupied and involved in
336 intramolecular hydrogen bonds in lignin molecules [54], thus reducing potential interactions with
337 coatings. The sharp decrease of WCA of control wood samples following weathering (from 80.0 ± 8.6 °
338 and 46.0 ± 5.8° to 49.3 ± 11.6 ° and 37.3 ± 6.4° for oak and beechwood samples, respectively) might
339 have occurred due to the degradation of wood hydrophobic components such as lignin under the effect
340 of UV light and water and leaching of their hydrophobic derivatives (esters, quinones and ketones),
341 which makes the wood surface richer in hydrophilic holocellulose [55]. Moreover, the microcracks
342 formed during weathering could favor water penetration and degradation of the surface [47]. After
343 exposure to UV weathering, WCA of all wood samples decreased by 22% to 25% of their initial value
344 for oak, and by 15% to 32% for beechwood. Nevertheless, the coatings efficiently protected the wooden
345 surfaces from cracks and brought an overall gain in water repellence before and after weathering when
346 compared to the control samples.

347 **Conclusions**

349 The sustainable coatings developed in this study displayed promising properties. Notably, the biocarbon
350 particles enhanced the colour stability and water repellence of the coatings and helped to maintain good
351 performance after artificial weathering. The increased absorbance in the UV and visible spectrums,
352 along with the decrease in particle size, suggests ways to further improve the coatings' performance by
353 introducing the smallest biocarbon particles possible into their formulation. Work is currently underway
354 to investigate using nanosized particles in various UV coating applications.

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